

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13860605

An Assessment Of Students Performance In English Language Test In Bayelsa State Tertiary Institutions

Ajoko Ebiyeladoh Laura¹ & Ubodiom Aminiasue²

¹Department of Nigerian Languages
Isaac Jasper Boro College of Education, Sagbama, Bayelsa State, Nigeria
lauraajoko@gmail.com

²Department of Library and Information Science
Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island, Bayelsa State, Nigeria
aminiasue19@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The study examined the assessment of students' performance in English Language Test in Bayelsa State. Tertiary Institutions. The study adopted the survey research design. The population of the study consists of 130 English Language lecturers in various tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State. The study develops a questionnaire instrument titled "Assessment of Students Performance in English Language Test" (ASPELT). The instrument is a three point likert scale questionnaire item. The instrument was subjected to face validation by an expert in the department of English Language in the University of Port Harcourt. The data obtained from the research questions was analyzed using simple mean, while the hypothesis was analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. Findings obtained from research question 1, table 1, showed that items 1, 2, 3 and 4 all agreed to the following questions. The response also showed that item 1, 2, 3 and 4 all had a mean value of 2.33, 2.78, 2.44 and 2.78 respectively. This shows that Poor infrastructure influences students' productivity, influences learners interest, influences students overall academic outcome and influences students preparation for classes in English Language Test in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State. Findings obtained from research question 2, table 2, showed that items 5, 6, 7 and 8 all agreed to the following questions. The response also showed that item 5, 6, 7 and 8 all had a mean value of 2.20, 2.10, 2.90 and 2.97 respectively. This shows that influence of poor teaching method retards students' performance, reduces the quality of graduates, affects the students' grade point average due to low examination scores and increases failure rate and reduce students confidence in English language. Findings obtained from research question 3, table 3, showed that items 9, 10, 11 and 12 all agreed to the following questions. The response also showed that item 9, 10, 11 and 12 all had a mean value of 2.56, 2.75, 2.44 and 2.30 respectively. This shows that students' self-confidence, Students belief system, institutional Value system and institutional cooperate interactions can enhance academic performance in English Language Test. Findings obtained from table 4 showed that r-calculated value of -0.129 are less than r-critical value of 0.666 at 0.05 level of significance and 7 degree of freedom. Based on the decision rule, the null hypothesis was accepted. Therefore, it was stated that there is no significant correlation on influence of poor infrastructure on students' performance and poor teaching method on students' performance in English language test in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State. The educational administrators should put in effort to build quality and modern infrastructures that will satisfy academic standards to encourage teaching and learning. Finally, it was recommended amongst others that seminars in the form of in-service training should be organized to develop lecturers in classroom teaching and learning.

Keywords: Assessment, Performance, English Language, Test, Tertiary Institutions

INTRODUCTION

Language is the major tool of communication in our in which discussion of language is possible. In their submission, Obisike et al. (2019) regard language as the human existence trademark in which communication of humans and their relationship with one another is made possible. Navidinia, Mobaraki and Malekzadeh (2019) opined that language is produced by speech for communication through a logical and consistence system. Santos (2019) explained that among the characteristics of man is the ability to send messages about events, situations and objects through language. The difference between man and animals is speech, man uses speech sounds for communication and English Language cannot be used very well without the effective manipulation of the speech sounds as far as for competence in linguistics is concerned. According to Kolawole and Oyinloye (2008), the most studied and generally desired language in the world is English Language, especially in the Nigerian society, starting from the nursery school to postsecondary school. It is a verbal behaviour governed by rules that have attained international scope (Omale, 2019). The importance of English Language in Nigeria cannot be over-emphasised.

Apart from the fact that it is the language used for instruction, it builds bridge across the barriers created by the existence of several ethnic groups and also serves as the official language with which communication is done in all facets of political, economic and social lives. In their submission, Jakobson and Halle (2016) averred that for language users to achieve an effective communication, then the morphological, syntactical, semantic and phonological ideals of the language must be maintained, otherwise, the language will not be properly communicated which also affect the language proficiency of the user. Oral communication is an avenue whereby the sounds of language are being put in so as to yield precise lexical items which results to acceptable syntactic structures due to its important to create effective communication between the speaker and the hearer, more so as an average of 70% of a normal person's working day is engaged in oral communication, invariably, man speaks more than he writes (Oyinloye, 2013). English pronunciation is an important subject since it provides the students with the required knowledge to fully comprehend and communicate in this language. By knowing the correct English pronunciation, the students are able to avoid misunderstanding in the language. Emphasizing the importance of pronunciation, Pourhosein (2016) explained that to pronounce is to make a meaningful sound. In the teaching and learning of pronunciation, its target is more than merely telling the learners to pronounce like the native speakers but emphasizes should be placed on pronouncing effectively. For effective pronunciation by the learners, learners should alter the way they think about the sounds of words and parts of speech such as stress pattern, rhythm and syllables.

One of the challenges students face in learning English Language is the use of poor teaching method. Teaching Method can best be defined as the type of principal & methods used for Instruction. There are many types of teaching methods, depending on what information or skill the teacher is trying to convey. Class participation demonstration, recitation and memorization are some of the teaching methods being used. When a teacher deciding in their method, they need to flexible and willing to adjust their style according to their student, student success in their academic achievement based on effect on effective teaching methods.

While the relationship between the compensation strategy & the academic success of the student was found to have a negative meaningful relation with academic success. However, the students the teachers were met cognitive strategies & compensation strategies. For effective teaching to take place, a good method must be adopted be a teacher. A teacher has many options when choosing a style, by which to teach. The teacher may write lesson plan of their own, borrow plans from other teacher, or search online, or within book for lesson plan. When deciding what method to use, a teacher needs to consider student background, knowledge, environment & learning goals. Teachers are aware that students have different way of absorbing information & of demonstrating their knowledge. Teacher often use to techniques which cater to multiple learning style to help students retain information & strength in understanding. A variety of strategies & method are used to ensure that all students have equal opportunities to learn.

Another significant factor affecting students' performance in English language is learning with poor infrastructure. The poor infrastructure here refers to classroom environment, libraries and general features needed by students for healthy classroom activities. When learning in an unfriendly and poor infrastructural environment student may perform poorly as truancy may become a daily norm. A classroom with broken roofs and bad unpainted buildings may discourage students from learning.

Also, socio-cultural factor may affect students' poor performance in English Language in most tertiary systems. The institution should have a culture of excellence by building sound value systems that will enable them meet up current academic goals. This value and academic culture enhance students' level of seriousness by associating with positive achievements. This can come with an institution maintaining certain standard practice or making uniform targets for students and lecturers. An institution with no goal for its self and students will produce poor graduate materials. This is so because many students would not be council and guided towards achieving academic goals.

Therefore there is the need to assess students' performance in English Language test in Bayelsa State tertiary institutions.

Statement of the Problem

Observation shows that students offering English language courses are having poor result as reported by departmental result officers in various tertiary institutions in the state. This may be as a result availability of poor infrastructural facility of teaching, quality of teachers and socio-cultural factor.

Purpose of the Study

The main objective of the study is to assessment of students' performance in English language test in Bayelsa State tertiary institutions. Specifically, the study sought to:

- i. Finds out the influence of poor infrastructure on students' performance in English Language Test in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State.
- ii. Find out the influence of poor teaching method on students' performance in English Language Test in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State.
- iii Find out influence socio-cultural effect on students' performance in English Language Test in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were developed and used for the study:

- i. What is the influence of poor infrastructure on students' performance in English Language Test in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State?
- ii. What is the influence of poor teaching method on students' performance in English Language Test in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State?
- iii What is the influence of socio-cultural effect on students' performance in English Language Test in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State?

Hypothesis

The null hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance.

There is no significant correlation on influence of poor infrastructure on students' performance and poor teaching method on students' performance in English language test in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State.

Scope of the Study

The study is limited to assessment of students' performance in English language test in Bayelsa State tertiary institutions.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Proficiency in Language and Communicative Competence

Proficiency in language is fundamentally viewed as the ability to make utilize language in communicative situations. Mäkelä (2005) opined that communicative competence has been the target of foreign language teaching since the early 1970s. Chomsky (1965) gave an introduction to the term, competence. He

differentiated between performance and competence, whereby performance is a situation where a speaker uses language in real life situations, and competence is where the speaker is conscious of the language and its structure. The Chomsky's ideas was further developed by Hymes (1972) further whereby he explained that communicative competence grammatical knowledge of language and the ability to use the language in social interactions. Chomsky's and Hyme's models which dealt in first language teaching later became a vital action that helped to make progress towards other frameworks. Canale and Swain later developed a model for second language teaching and testing purposes in 1980 in which the model influenced the comprehension of communicative competence. The model of Canale and Swain (1980) divided communicative competence into three diverse competences such as sociolinguistics competence, strategic grammatical competence and grammatical competence. Bachman and Palmer (1996) also enlarged the Canale and Swain's model of communicative competence for testing by including more detailed information about personal and test-related characteristics that affect an individual's test performance.

Student achievement has become a hot topic in education today, especially with increased accountability for classroom teachers. The ultimate goal for any teacher is to improve the ability level and prepare students for adulthood. Defining student achievement and factors that impact progress is critical to becoming a successful teacher. Student achievement measures the amount of academic content a student learns in a determined amount of time. Each grade level has learning goals or instructional standards and teaching methods that educators are required to teach. Student achievement will increase when quality of Teaching methods are used to teach instructional standards and properly. There are many variables that can impact successful student achievement, but the most critical are classroom instruction and method of teaching. It is important to remember that all students do not learn the same way or at the same rate. Students are like leaves on a tree; there are no two exactly the same. Just as a leaf comes in unique colors, shapes and sizes, each student has their own unique learning style. Classroom instruction or teaching method is the most important factor that impacts student achievement. A good teacher will use strategies such as discussion among students, videos, or stories, to gain student attention and to support the learning process. You should constantly be thinking of ways to make learning fun and appropriate. For example, in looking at our to-do list, you may pre-pay for your cleaning to get a discount or join a friend to make the study session more interesting. Likewise, student achievement involves well-thought out strategies to improve the quality of learning! According to teaching is a continuous process that involves bringing about desirable changes in learners through use of appropriate methods. Indicated that in order to bring desirable changes in students, teaching methods used by educators should be best for the subject matter. Furthermore, sustained that teaching methods work effectively mainly if they suit learners' needs since every learner interprets and responds to questions in a unique way. As such, alignment of teaching methods with students' needs and preferred learning influence students' academic attainments. Teaching method can be classified into three ways like Teacher-Centered Methods: Under this method, students simply obtain information from the teacher without building their engagement level with the subject being taught. The approach is least practical, more theoretical and memorizing It does not apply activity based learning to encourage students to learn real life problems based on applied knowledge. Since the teacher controls the transmission and sharing of knowledge, the lecturer may attempt to maximize the delivery of information while minimizing time and effort. As a result, both interest and understanding of students may get lost.

METHODS

The study adopted the survey research design. The survey research design was used because questionnaire items were distributed to respondents to fill to obtain relevant information for the study. The population of the study consists of 130 English Language lecturers in various tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State. This was obtained through the information provided by the head of department of English Language in the various tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State. The study develop a questionnaire

instrument titled" Assessment of Students Performance in English Language Test " (ASPELT). The instrument is a three point likert scale questionnaire item. The options are arranged as Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A) and Disagree (D). The response options were weighed as 3, 2 and 1 respectively. The instrument consists of twelve (12) items.

The instrument was subjected to face validation by an expert in the department of English Language in the University of Port Harcourt. The expert checked the language content of the instrument and made necessary corrections before final copy was produced and sent to field for study. Test-retest method was used to obtain the reliability of the instrument. A Pilot study was conducted with five (5) language experts in various Rivers State University, Port Harcourt. ASPELT instrument was administered to respondents to fill. The scores obtained from the test was recorded and submitted. After two weeks, the same instrument was administered to the same set of respondents to fill. The scores obtained again was recorded and submitted. The two scores obtained at different intervals were computed and analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. The r-value obtained from the study was calculated to be 0.78 which was considered adequate for the study.

The data obtained from the research questions was analyzed using simple mean, while the hypothesis was analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. The hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance. For decision rule if r-calculated value is less than r-tabulated value, the null hypothesis was accepted. But if r-calculated value is higher than r-tabulated value, the null hypothesis will be rejected.

DATA ANALYSIS

Research Question One: *What is the influence of poor infrastructure on students’ performance in English Language Test in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State?*

Table 1: Influence of poor infrastructure on students’ performance in English Language Test in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State

S/N	Items	Mean	Decision
1	Poor infrastructure influences students productivity in English Language Test in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State	2.33	Agree
2	Poor infrastructure influences learners interest in English Language Test in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State	2.78	Agree
3	Poor infrastructure influences students overall academic outcome in English Language Test in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State	2.44	Agree
4	Poor infrastructure influences students preparation for classes in English Language Test in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State	2.78	Agree
	Total	10.33	

Findings obtained from research question 1, table 1, showed that items 1, 2, 3 and 4 all agreed to the following questions. The response also showed that item 1, 2, 3 and 4 all had a mean value of 2.33, 2.78, 2.44 and 2.78 respectively. This shows that Poor infrastructure influences students’ productivity, influences learners interest, influences students overall academic outcome and influences students preparation for classes in English Language Test in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State.

Research Question Two: *What is the influence of poor teaching method on students' performance in English Language Test in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State?*

Table 2: Influence of poor teaching method on students' performance in English Language Test in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State

S/N	Items	Mean	Decision
5	Influence of poor teaching method retards students' performance in English language	2.20	Agree
6	Poor Teaching method reduces the quality of graduates in English Language Department in Tertiary Institutions in Bayelsa State	2.10	Agree
7	Poor Teaching method affects the students' grade point average due to low examination scores in English language department.	2.90	Agree
8	Poor Teaching method increases failure rate and reduce students confidence in English Language department.	2.97	Agree
	Total	10.17	

Findings obtained from research question 2, table 2, showed that items 5, 6, 7 and 8 all agreed to the following questions. The response also showed that item 5, 6, 7 and 8 all had a mean value of 2.20, 2.10, 2.90 and 2.97 respectively. This shows that influence of poor teaching method retards students' performance, reduces the quality of graduates, affects the students' grade point average due to low examination scores and increases failure rate and reduce students confidence in English language.

Research Question Three: *What is the influence socio-cultural effect on students' performance in English Language Test in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State?*

Table 3: Influence of socio-cultural effect on students' performance in English Language Test in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State

S/N	Items	Mean	Decision
9	Students self-confidence can enhance academic performance in English Language Test	2.56	Agree
10	Students belief system can enhance academic performance in English Language department	2.75	Agree
11	Institutional Value system can boast students' academic performance in English Language department	2.44	Agree
12	Institutional cooperate interactions can enhance students' academic performance in English Language department	2.30	Agree
	Total	10.05	

Findings obtained from research question 3, table 3, showed that items 9, 10, 11 and 12 all agreed to the following questions. The response also showed that item 9, 10, 11 and 12 all had a mean value of 2.56, 2.75, 2.44 and 2.30 respectively. This shows that students' self-confidence, Students belief system, institutional Value system and institutional cooperate interactions can enhance academic performance in English Language Test.

Hypothesis

There is no significant correlation on influence of poor infrastructure on students' performance and poor teaching method on students' performance in English language test in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State.

Table 4: Correlation on influence of poor infrastructure on students' performance and poor teaching method on students' performance in English language test in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State

S/N	X(Influence of poor infrastructure on students' performance)	Y(poor teaching method on students' performance in English language test)	X ²	Y ²	XY
1	2.33	2.20	5.42	4.84	5.13
2	2.78	2.10	7.73	4.41	5.83
3	2.44	2.90	5.95	8.41	7.08
4	2.78	2.97	7.73	8.82	8.26
	Σ=10.33	Σ=10.17	Σ=26.83	Σ=26.48	Σ=26.30

Findings obtained from table 4 showed that r-calculated value of -0.129 are less than r-critical value of 0.666 at 0.05 level of significance and 7 degree of freedom. Based on the decision rule, the null hypothesis was accepted. Therefore, it was stated that there is no significant correlation on influence of poor infrastructure on students' performance and poor teaching method on students' performance in English language test in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Findings obtained from research question 1, table 1, showed that items 1, 2, 3 and 4 all agreed to the following questions. The response also showed that item 1, 2, 3 and 4 all had a mean value of 2.33, 2.78, 2.44 and 2.78 respectively. This shows that Poor infrastructure influences students' productivity, influences learners interest, influences students overall academic outcome and influences students preparation for classes in English Language Test in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State. According to Sukyad & Mardiani (2011) poor infrastructure has affected students' academic productivity in many ways.

Findings obtained from research question 2, table 2, showed that items 5, 6, 7 and 8 all agreed to the following questions. The response also showed that item 5, 6, 7 and 8 all had a mean value of 2.20, 2.10, 2.90 and 2.97 respectively. This shows that influence of poor teaching method retards students' performance, reduces the quality of graduates, affects the students' grade point average due to low examination scores and increases failure rate and reduce students confidence in English language. Jacobson and Halle, (2016) explained that poor academic infrastructure encourage truant attitude among students thus making them perform poorly in examinations.

Findings obtained from research question 3, table 3, showed that items 9, 10, 11 and 12 all agreed to the following questions. The response also showed that item 9, 10, 11 and 12 all had a mean value of 2.56, 2.75, 2.44 and 2.30 respectively. This shows that students' self-confidence, Students belief system, institutional Value system and institutional cooperate interactions can enhance academic performance in English Language Test. Jolayemi & Oyinloye, (2019) stated poor value system reduces students discipline and attitude to learn.

Findings obtained from table 4 showed that r-calculated value of -0.129 are less than r-critical value of 0.666 at 0.05 level of significance and 7 degree of freedom. Based on the decision rule, the null hypothesis was accepted. Therefore, it was stated that there is no significant correlation on influence of poor infrastructure on students' performance and poor teaching method on students' performance in English language test in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State. Egwuogu, (2012) revealed that an educational environment with poor infrastructure also discourages teachers and students to have healthy conversation.

CONCLUSION

The study showed that influence of poor infrastructure, teaching method and socio-cultural system influences students' performance in English Language Test in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The study made the following recommendations based on the findings obtained in the study:

1. The educational administrators should put in effort to build quality and modern infrastructures that will satisfy academic standards to encourage teaching and learning.
2. Seminars in the form of in-service training should be organized to develop lecturers in classroom teaching and learning.
3. The school administration should initiate value system that will condition students to maintain a mind frame of academic excellence.

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